

Success Factors of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Implementation in Higher Education Institutions: Case Study of MUET, Sindh

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Abstract:

Higher education Institution (HEIs) around the globe is presently experiencing imperative changes to how they cooperate with the understudies, administration, faculty members and students. The majority of these establishments Concentrate for the most part on approaches to decrease costs and be powerful in the way they react to customer needs, and in this way pick up an aggressive Feature. Many of institutions, the concept of customer relationship management (CRM) is one, especially the education market becomes more competitive. There is a strong system of customer relationship management can help organizations gain unexpected, but important, advantage in high market higher education competitive. Ultimately, all of these factors combine to provide students with a sense of greater value. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a terminology that represents a business strategy built around the concept of improving customer services. CRM aims to increase customer satisfactions and thus increases the business income. It has been observed that the CRM not exploited on a large scale among the under developing countries such as Pakistan, especially in the higher education institutions higher education institutions (HEIs). Our findings suggest that a clear understanding of student life cycle will be more likely to adopt CRM. We propose that a fit between the choice of CRM goal strategic versus transactional CRM and organizational factors will help determine the continuous adoption of CRM by higher education users. This study examines why the critical success factors of CRM implementation, which HIEs especially in the MUET In the Engineering University have look to implement CRM and help them achieve their goals system.

Keywords: CRM, Customer Relationship Management, Higher Education Institutions, HEIs, MUET, Pakistan

1. Introduction

The adequacy of CRM is about to get a check and transfer of information for clients and for the rapid and appropriate support for the client. CRM gives the perspective of integrated customer communications ranging from programming applications that capture and with these blocs information convincing study to detect the data shrouded expected to strengthen the relationship between organizations with customers and necessary. Think of a fundamental rise in CRM recently to offer clients the most vital assets of organizations. Through deep investigation of customers, retailers can take care of customer orders and the expansion of benefits. (Ceolin, 2000) study of customer relationship management (CRM) business as a methodology that uses the power of innovation to connect all parts of the question of the organization in order to build customer unwaveringness in the long term. (Goodhue et al., 2002) to achieve business benefits through customer relationship management. Customer relationship management (CRM) is the image of the data and raise the level of Foundation.

Dick Lee (2000), and the state which is seen CRM as the "chain" response, which is created by the new main activities to connect with customers when they are to accomplish the state unnatural to improve innovation data and the requirement for consistent excellence on the management of quality clients. Thomson (2002), "Master CRM", and removes the meaning of CRM: in the area of enormous business, regardless of the fact that it only includes a small number of individuals, and there is no spare no total figure until all the data through various media. After the parts, it should be displayed for the "right people" "session in a timely manner." For this reason, computers, programming, online animation.

But the foundation movement can take into account this information only when handling and information on the intentions of the options to be taken to withdraw or maintain customer premise. Obviously, it's important to be private media, through which method is to visualize the activation methods and improve the option to take the same action.

It was seen on an extensive scale for client relationship administration (CRM) as a procedure identified with the development division and client maintenance through enhanced communication and administration. Changes in the nature of the clients, and their conduct because of the handled items are liable to have an immediate effect on the organization's execution and it additionally has suggestions for choice making on a technique to enhance the association with clients later on readiness. It is perceived that not every client is just as imperative association as far as him/ her the estimation of life, and accordingly, clients need to be portioned with a specific end goal to focus the client of key significance.

(Jutla et al., 2001) portray CRM in terms of access, dissect and learn and to give customers. (Boerne player Sparta et al., 2004) is the assessment of CRM going to take advantage of interest in the client connection to promote an aggressive position and expand profits. Interpretation needs behind whittling down of the client to be distinguished and successful measures to be taken to address this issue. This required data on customer's designs and behavior tendencies. Customer relationship management is a broad term for overseeing the business associations with clients to strengthen the relationship and dedication.

The current study may benefit university administration, managers and policy makers to enhance the satisfaction level of the students and their guardians and assist them towards the establishment of quality services, as well as increase the quality ratings of HEIs. Yin (2003 & 2009) explained that the case study based research methodology investigates a contemporary phenomenon within real life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomena and context are not cleanly evident.

The administration should move in the direction of making culture that is based on the "benefit more prominent in the last" instead of "individual increase" (Flory.2014).

This paper, thus investigates the same scenario for Mehran university of Engineering & Technology (MUET), Jamshoro. Moreover, the results of this study may be replicated to other organizations as well. The lack of CRM implementation in HEIs, could be due to many reasons ranging from administrative issues to unawareness towards the benefits of CRM implementation.

This paper Literature has been used to review the data collection for Mehran university of Engineering & Technology (MUET), Jamshoro this study, where peer reviewed the main sources used. In spite of frequent studies It indicates a different CRM, this study focused on four factors. People, technology, process and culture. Moreover, the recommendations of the Over the universities in the Developed and developing nations which should be implemented CRM Successfully been supplied.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The various stakeholders of university such as students, faculty, management, administration, alumni and other external actors are added into the group of sample. About 600 questionnaires are diffused with the rate of return as 50% approximately.

TABLE 1 SAMPLE DISTRIBUTION

University	Distribution of questioner	Response achieved
Administration	200	81
Faculty	200	65
Students	200	126
Total	600	272

Question of the survey are framed based on literature review and result earlier research conducted by

i-e: Mahar et al, [1] . main questions asked from the respondents:

1. Do you measure the customer Management implementation success factors?
2. How important are the factors for the customer management implementation?
3. Is there a defined strategy for the customer management implementation?
4. Does organization consider customer management implementation as a pure technology?
5. What factors are most relevant to their component such as people ,process, and information technology ?

The response was based on five points measured on likert scale which are strongly agree to strongly disagree. On the collected data reliability test was also conducted. Finding's of the reliable data through Cronbach's Alpha descriptive analysis tests were also conducted through SPSS to test the data. After perfect measurement statistical tests the main findings are discovered.

TABLE: 2 Reliability test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
0836	48

3. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

3.1 Strategy for the implementing Customer Management

According to the crosstab chart two type of options given by respondent, Yes and No. if we analysis the results of yes option, it shows that administration are equal about 20%.and faculty about below20% and students result is about 40%.while when we are looking from No option the result showing that administrations results are about 58%then faculty is about 50%and students are about 70% saying that there is not particular defined strategy for implementing the Customer management.

Fig.3.1: strategy for implementing CRM

Source: survey result

3.2 Customer management implementation as a pure technology

According to the crosstab chart two type of options given by respondent, yes and no. if we analysis the results of Yes option, it shows that faculty about 40% and administration are equal about 25%.and students result is about 80%.while when we are looking from No option the result showing that administrations results are about 55%then faculty is about 20%and students are about 25% saying that there is no particular defined the customer Management implementation as a pure technology considered .

Fig.3.2: Customer management implementation as a pure technology

Source: survey result

3.3 Measurement for the customer Management implementation success factors

According to the crosstab chart two type of options given by respondent, yes and no. if we analysis the results of Yes option, it shows that faculty about 58% and administration are equal about 60%.and students result is about 60%.while when we are looking from No option the result showing that administrations results are about 40%then faculty is about 30%and students are about 50% saying that there is no particular defined the organization aware of the existence success for its customer Management implementation.

Fig.3.3: Measurement for the customer Management implementation success factors

Source: survey result

3.4 CRM PROCEDURES BY WHICH ORGANIZATION IMPLEMENT CUSTOMER MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

The factors used in graph are importance of clear customer experience strategy, to selecting the correct people ,to developing, motivating and managing your people, to establishing effective service delivery processes, to structure in continuous improvement , to ensuring managers are the key change-agents.all factors denoted different procedures by which organization implement CRM all are equal about 60% to 80%. Which means there is need for apply CRM procedures.

the findings of graph showing that if we improve access services then all other things will be managed automatically.

Fig.3.4 CRM procedures by which organization implement Customer management strategy
Source: survey result

3.5 SUCCESS FACTORS OF CRM

The results are given in graph in cluster form. the question are arranged together in which we shows the percentages regarding to top management ,in which 60% respondents are selected to highly important option. Other question given is to customer management strategy in which response is 52% who are selected to important. Next question is to data management in which 52% respondents are selected to highly important option. The next question is to cultural changes, in which respondents are 77% are selected to important option. The other question is to process change the respondents are 58% selected to highly important option. The next question is to skillful motivated and trend staff, the respondents who are selected to important option 49%. The other question is to customer involvement/consultation whose respondents are 52% who are selected to highly important option.

The last question in the cluster is to inter departmental integration in which respondents are 36% are selected to highly important option. The findings can be described here that the whole question cluster is about the to ask about the success factors of implementation of CRM The mostly respondents are agreed in the implementation of the CRM success. as we see the highest percentage in the cluster of questions the we have to manage the daily workflow of process in university which needs the improvement in the process and which can accomplished through CRM.

Fig.3.5: Success factors of CRM
Source: survey result

3.6 Factors Relevent Components

The results are given in graph in cluster form. the question are arranged together in which we shows the percentages regarding to top management ,in which 96% respondents are selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology . Other question given is to customer management strategy in which response is 95% who are selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. Next question is to data management in which 97% respondents are selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. The next question is to cultural changes, in which respondents are 97% selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. The other question is to process change the respondents are 97% selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. The next question is to skillful motivated and trend staff, the respondents who are 96%. The other question is to customer involvement/consultation whose respondents are 94% who are selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. The last question in the cluster is to inter departmental integration in which respondents are 96% are selected to multiple choice option such as people business process technology. The findings can be described here that the whole question cluster is about the to ask about the success factors relevant components of implementation of CRM The mostly respondents are agreed in the implementation of the CRM success relevant components as we see the highest percentage in the cluster of questions the we have to manage the daily workflow of process in university which needs the improvement in the process and which can accomplished through CRM.

Fig.3.6: Factors Relevant Components

Source: survey result

DISCUSSION

The main perseverance of this study is to generate further knowledge and understanding in calculating the impression of CRM implementation in higher education institutions for developed and developing nations. For instance, in Pakistan study on the implementation of CRM is the beginning of his eye and here is the existence of a permanent gap in the perceptions of implementation, so the aim of this study is to bridge that gap and prove that knowledge about the contribution of implementation to a large extent. One of important results indicated that the participants in all the university departments have shown that there is a need for CRM implementation of higher education institutions for the activities of developed and developing countries of university research, did not have a large part of the participants basic knowledge about CRM and customer management implementation relation-ship management, there is a shortage training, technology and management support, in addition to that there also appeared to lack of awareness on the implementation of CRM, because the performance of Pakistan to contribute to the low economic growth, universities, so it should be Pakistani universities focus the production of e CRM, and therefore should be focused on the implementation of CRM.

CONCLUSIONS

In this research the problem of students, faculty, and administration within MUET Jamshoro carried out that the significant portion of respondents does not have basic knowledge about CRM terminology they have not a clear plan and implementation which does not nominate what is actually the CRM ? It is a business process related to peoples which involves developing change management not the information system. That might be changes business process of your institution for much CRM instead of trying to influence the CRM to what you going to do. It is expected not to change main system with CRM. It is also essential to check that it work together rather creating duplicate information.

That will be cheaper and possibly make more money and also have happy customers. Due to unawareness, hence it is proposed that university management need to organize training programs which will have enough committed resources for accomplishment that includes for help to create an awareness regarding CRM implementation then it will help to implement a proper system as developed countries have, yes that whole process is not an ready solution that needs proper uphold properly and maintain.

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